

CONCEPT OF IMPROVEMENT PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF ESP STUDENTS BY CLIL

(Content and Language Integrated Learning)

Tashkent Institute of Finance

“Foreign Languages” department

(PhD) Ataeva Nilufar Saliyevna

Annotation It provides students of higher educational institutions of economics with the opportunity to learn foreign languages, especially English, to develop the skills of market economy relations and to focus economic education on the profession.

Key words: provide, student, competence, professional, improvement, language

The main purpose of English language teaching is to increase the cognitive activity of students in ensuring the vocational orientation of economic education. In addition to increasing students' knowledge, ingenuity, and cognitive activity, while teaching English in higher educational institutions of economics, it is possible to form their spiritual, moral, and human qualities, orient them to the economic profession, and develop their professional training.

So, using the types of speech activities in teaching English, the student will have the opportunity to get information from the text he has read or listened to in English, to answer questions to explain its content, and to express his attitude to the received information. As a result, it builds intellectual skills and competencies in future economists and improves their career orientation. It can be seen that foreign languages have a special role in strengthening the ideological consciousness of future economists studying in higher educational institutions of economics, in their development as well-rounded adults, and in ensuring that economic education is oriented towards the profession.

Of course, although the names of the components of teaching English in higher education institutions, educational conditions, teaching goals and content are similar, they differ from each other in terms of quality and quantity. In the economic education system, it is very important to take into account the students' interest and level of knowledge of the language through the teaching of the English language in the direction of the economic profession.

It is known that the high number of study hours, which is considered as a component of educational conditions, is one of the main factors that have a positive effect on the educational process. Therefore, in higher education institutions of economics, there are not enough lesson hours allocated in the curriculum for students to master the English language thoroughly and to use it widely in their professional activities as an economist in the future. Therefore, it is necessary to pay great attention to extracurricular activities. It is appropriate to plan teaching English to students in the higher educational institutions of economics in optional or foreign language study circles. It is known that due to the integration of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the world community in all aspects of its social life, the need to learn English is increasing. Therefore, the current demand demands that future economists in higher educational institutions of economics study and master the English language.

Of course, the development of non-state sectors in the economy, integration into the economic system of our country in the teaching of foreign languages, including English, requires redefining the issues facing modern education. From this point of view, today, one of the most urgent issues is to increase the economic literacy of future economic personnel by teaching them foreign languages, including English. For this, it is necessary to establish consistency of economic education with teaching foreign languages in higher educational institutions of economics. The organization of extracurricular facultative courses, practical training, and various events on economic education in foreign languages, especially in English, has a positive effect.

Studying various economic issues based on the knowledge acquired from other academic subjects, as well as English, and real-life examples will further develop students' creative abilities. In addition to classes, economic literacy training and events in foreign languages, namely English, are not only a factor in strengthening future economists' economic knowledge, but also a factor in learning foreign languages, namely English.

It provides students of higher educational institutions of economics with the opportunity to learn foreign languages, especially English, to develop the skills of market economy relations and to focus economic education on the profession. Therefore, it is one of the important issues to develop economic literacy and economic thinking of the economists who are responsible for the fate and future of our country by teaching them foreign languages, especially English.

One of the ways to direct students to the profession of an economist and improve their professional training is to teach foreign languages to graduates of higher educational institutions of economics, and in order to raise this field to a high level, it is necessary to make appropriate use of the possibilities of methods of teaching one of the foreign languages, in particular, English. The study of the experience of training economists in economic higher educational institutions of our republic shows that even one higher educational institution has all the opportunities to form individual characteristics in a student. Foreign languages have a great role in this. Because learning foreign languages, especially English, not only allows students to know foreign languages, but also to form a person from a spiritual and moral point of view, to create conditions for the development of professional qualities in future economists.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmanova (1969) Dictionary of linguistic terms. M.: Encyclopedia 607 p.;
2. Akhmedov O.S. (2016) Linguistic analysis and translation problems of tax and customs terms in English and Uzbek Languages-T.
3. Melnikov G.P. (1991) Fundamental of terminology. M.: 3p

4.Reformatskiy A.A. (1967) History introduction to linguistic M.